

UTILIZATION OF RPMS CLASSROOM OBSERVATION TOOL AMONG MAPEH TEACHERS IN TACLOBAN CITY DIVISION

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Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tool among MAPEH Teachers in Tacloban City Division

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Abstract

The study assessed the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool among MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City Division. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, involving 73 public junior high school MAPEH teachers from Tacloban City Division as respondents. The findings revealed that most MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City Division are below middle-aged, female, with over 10 years of experience, possess a Baccalaureate Degree with Master's Units; and mostly proficient teachers. Moreover, the majority of trainings and seminars are local, with lower participation rates at higher seminar levels. Classroom observation tools are "Fully Utilized" for proficient and highly proficient teachers, regardless of school size. The study found no significant correlation between profile variables and utilization, and no significant differences in utilization across different school categories. It is advised that Junior High School MAPEH teachers seek professional development and post-graduate coursework, while DepEd Tacloban officials should promote collaboration, resource utilization, and feedback among teachers for enhanced teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: *utilization, RPMS Classroom Observation Tool, MAPEH teachers*

Introduction

Classroom observation is a form of accountability that encourages the assessment of teachers' abilities to uphold standards, refine instructional methods, and improve student learning outcomes. Classroom observation is a requirement for maintaining effective education in the Philippines, as mandated by Republic Act 10533, sometimes referred to as the K to 12 Law. As per Section 14 of the law, the Department of Education would provide a report on several areas of implementation, such as teacher well-being and training requirements, which can be assessed through observing teachers in the classroom. Classroom Observation Tools evaluate instruction and learning activities, enhancing the teachers' classroom practice and providing them with constructive feedback, as defined by the Department of Education (2018). Feedback provides valuable input for continuous improvement and allows for the exchange of ideas and expertise.

The Professional Standards for Teachers encompass the K–12 teacher quality standard, which evaluates the caliber of a teacher's classroom performance. Asio and Riego de Dios (2019) discussed some professional characteristics that a teacher should possess. A classroom observation tool has been created to evaluate classroom activities according to the recently established professional standards. This tool aims to highlight both strengths and areas that need improvement. The objective is to precisely design professional development programs that are customized to meet the individual requirements of teachers.

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers - Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS) according to DepEd Order No. 42 s. 2017, requires classroom observation. It grew increasingly objective and standardized. The reason for its usage is to facilitate mentorship, coaching, performance evaluation, and feedback. This resource assists educators in their continuous professional growth (Department of Education, 2017). Conforming to Suparto (2020), the combination of academic supervision and classroom observation approaches has the potential to enhance the quality of teacher practice.

The utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tool can impact the academic success and future career of both students and teachers. Without objective and consistent classroom observations, the quality of instruction and the educational system may suffer from a lack of accurate, reliable, and valid evaluation information. Hence, the researcher aims to assess the utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tool among MAPEH teachers in the Tacloban City Division.

Researchers have, therefore, examined the relationship between a range of characteristics and classroom observation tools; nevertheless, significant gaps remain in the literature that require further investigation. In particular, very little to no research has examined the assessment of the RPMS's implementation or utilization and its effect on teachers' performance (Mamaug, 2022).

In the Philippine context, the alignment of observation tools such as the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) with the actual needs and challenges faced by local teachers is also a concern (Garcia et al., 2020). Misalignment can lead to observations that do not accurately reflect or improve the targeted educational practices. Addressing these issues is critical to enhancing the efficacy and applicability of classroom observation tools, ensuring they effectively contribute to educational advancements in diverse settings.

The Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tool is designed to enhance teacher performance by providing structured and consistent feedback. While this tool is broadly implemented across various subjects, its specific impact and utilization among Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) teachers remains under-explored. Most studies and evaluations of the RPMS Classroom Observation Tool focus on core subjects like Mathematics, Science, and Language Arts. MAPEH, with its unique pedagogical requirements, often demands a different approach. The existing literature lacks detailed

analysis on how the RPMS tool addresses the specific needs and challenges faced by MAPEH teachers. Similarly, research on the RPMS tool's effectiveness is often conducted in a generic or nationwide context. There is limited understanding of how regional factors, such as those specific to Tacloban City Division, influence the utilization and effectiveness of the tool. Tacloban, with its distinct cultural, economic, and educational landscape, may present unique challenges and opportunities that are not captured in broader studies.

This research is justified by important issues pertaining to the use of tools for classroom observation. The Philippines' empirical data shows that there is a deficiency in these instruments' efficacy and use. Studies have revealed, for example, that a large number of teachers score worse on measures pertaining to the use of diverse and culturally relevant teaching practices, which has a direct effect on student engagement and learning outcomes (Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021).

Moreover, national data indicates that even with the RPMS's structured framework, its application and assessors' level of skill might differ greatly, which can result in discrepancies in teacher evaluations and professional growth (Mamaug, 2022). This disparity calls for a targeted investigation to identify the particular difficulties and opportunities for development in the Tacloban City Division, ultimately supporting the more general objective of raising educational standards via efficient teacher evaluation and development.

In order to close a significant gap in knowledge, this study looked into the relationship between profile variables and tool utilization. Furthermore, this study intends to further our comprehension of how RPMS technologies can be successfully used in various educational contexts by investigating the degree of utilization across various school categories.

The study aimed to assess the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool among MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City Division. The researcher argued that there is a need to assess the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool among MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City Division so that alternatives can be offered and pertinent recommendations for professional & organizational development can be created. Truly, we are unable to provide feasible solutions to an issue until we have completed a "diagnosis." And in the case of junior high school MAPEH teachers in the Division of Tacloban City, assessing the utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tool is the very first step in addressing the problem.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by determining the extent of utilization of the RPMS Classroom Observation Tool among MAPEH teachers and suggest ways on how to improve classroom observations in the Department of Education.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tool among MAPEH Teachers in Tacloban City Division for school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of MAPEH teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. length of service;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. position / rank;
 - 1.6. relevant training and seminars attended?
2. What is the extent of the utilization of the RPMS Classroom Observation Tools for highly proficient and proficient teachers in the following school categories:
 - 2.1. small school;
 - 2.2. medium school;
 - 2.3. large school; and
 - 2.4. mega school?
3. Is there a significant relationship between profile variable and the extent of utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tools?
4. Is there a significant difference in the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools based among school categories?

Literature Review

Profile of MAPEH Teachers

The use of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tool by MAPEH teachers is an important topic of research, particularly in terms of determining how demographic characteristics influence its implementation and efficacy (Asio & Jimenez, 2020). The MAPEH teacher profile, which includes age, gender, length of service, educational attainment, position/rank, and appropriate training and seminars attended, provides a thorough backdrop for studying the RPMS tool's deployment (Corcelles et al., 2020).

Several demographic factors impact the use of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tool by MAPEH teachers. Research suggests that age has a key role, with younger teachers being more adaptive and receptive to

incorporating new technologies and instructional practices (Ghavifekr et al., 2019). On the other hand, senior educators might still use conventional techniques, but their wealth of knowledge can be useful in observations (Suparto, 2020). Sex also matters since research indicates that compared to their male counterparts, the adoption of collaborative and student-driven teaching practices is more common among female educators. (De la Cruz, 2019). This distinction might have an impact on how male and female educators react to and apply observations-based feedback in the classroom.

A teacher's approach to instruction and classroom management is greatly influenced by their length of service. Longer tenured teachers typically possess a greater comprehension of the requirements of their students and the school climate, which can improve the efficacy of observations in the classroom (Asio & Jimenez, 2020). The necessity for specialized professional development programs is highlighted by the possibility that they will also be resistant to change (Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021). The impact of educational attainment on teaching practices and the use of observation tools is evident. Teachers with higher qualifications are typically more adept at implementing a variety of instructional tactics and putting theory into practice (Lopez, 2018). Based on observations made in the classroom, this advanced knowledge may result in more helpful feedback (Basco-Galangco, 2018).

The duties and demands imposed on teachers are determined by their position or rank, which is divided into Highly Proficient and Proficient Teachers. According to the Department of Education (2020), Highly Proficient Teachers (Master Teachers I through IV) are intended to set high standards, coach other teachers, and exhibit great teaching techniques. Particular indicators that highlight their advanced abilities and leadership responsibilities are part of the RPMS tools for Highly Proficient Teachers (DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023).

Teachers I-III who are considered proficient must fulfill the fundamental standards of the teaching profession and continually enhance their methods. Fundamental teaching abilities and capabilities that enhance student learning are the main emphasis of the RPMS tools for Proficient Teachers (Department of Education, 2020). As per Ghavifekr et al. (2019), these instruments aid in pinpointing opportunities for improvement and offer a foundation for career advancement. Teachers can improve their teaching skills and adjust to changing educational trends by attending pertinent training and seminars. Teachers can stay current on the newest teaching pedagogies and classroom management tactics by participating in workshops and seminars that provide ongoing professional development (Corcelles et al., 2020). Taking part in these training sessions gives instructors the tools they need to achieve the performance metrics defined by the RPMS, which is vital for making successful use of classroom observation tools (Suparto, 2020).

The RPMS Classroom Observation Tool's use is thus greatly influenced by the characteristics of MAPEH teachers, such as their age, sex, length of service, level of education, position/rank, and involvement in pertinent trainings and seminars. Designing focused professional development programs and enhancing the general efficacy of classroom observations require an understanding of these demographic aspects.

Utilization of the RPMS Classroom Observation Tools

There are notable differences in the way that various school categories use the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tools (De la Cruz, 2019). In small, medium, large, and mega schools, this section examines the use rates of highly proficient and proficient teachers (Department of Education, 2020; Suparto, 2020).

Small schools, which are frequently distinguished by a small student body and faculty, have particular difficulties when implementing RPMS Classroom Observation Tools. Studies show that these institutions' smaller size enables more frequent and individualized observations, although the efficiency of these assessments may be constrained by limited resources. De Vera and Gonzales (2020) assert that closer teacher-student interactions are advantageous for small schools since they can improve the application of observation feedback. The complete use of RPMS tools, however, can be hampered by a lack of professional development opportunities and administrative support.

Because medium-sized schools usually have greater resources than small schools, the RPMS Classroom Observation Tools can be implemented in a more structured manner. Research indicates that medium-sized schools are able to strike a balance between providing professional development opportunities and individualized feedback. The Department of Education (2020), for example, notes that medium schools frequently have staff members who are specifically designated for mentoring and coaching, which facilitates the efficient use of RPMS technologies. However, Ghavifekr et al. (2019) point out that because of different administrative methods, medium schools can still have trouble remaining impartial and consistent in their observations.

Similarly, RPMS Classroom Observation Tools are typically used in larger schools in a more methodical and thorough manner. These educational institutions benefit from a wealth of resources and highly qualified personnel who can perform thorough and frequent observations. Lopez (2018) asserts that larger schools have the capacity to establish a more stringent observation program, guaranteeing prompt and useful input. The feedback process could be slowed down by bureaucratic obstacles brought about by the increased scale, though. To lessen these difficulties, Basco-Galangco (2018) highlights the significance of precise communication and organized observation procedures.

Moreover, mega schools offer opportunities and challenges for the use of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools due to their large student numbers and extensive faculty. Mega schools are able to implement modern observation technology and complete professional

development programs due to their abundance of resources. According to De la Cruz (2019), full-time instructional coaches with expertise in conducting and analyzing classroom observations are frequently employed by mega schools. Nonetheless, the sheer magnitude of these establishments may result in irregularities in the methods of observation and the application of feedback. According to Suparto (2020), large schools should set up reliable procedures to guarantee accuracy and consistency while using RPMS instruments.

Classroom observation is a teaching method that evaluates teaching and learning by closely observing teacher-student interactions and the classroom environment. It provides insights into strengths and weaknesses, aids in improvement, and offers feedback for teachers and professional development (Sebastian, 2020). There are observations made in every classroom. Observations are conducted during a teacher's career as a routine administrative measure or as a component of supervision. Classroom observations provide a valuable opportunity to evaluate one's own work, improve skills, and uncover areas of strength (Melati, 2019). In the worst-case scenario, they could be stressful and challenge the observer's faith. Classroom observation serves as a training method and support system for teachers who employ structured periods of planning, observation, and thorough analysis of their teaching performances. This is particularly beneficial for novice teachers who may lack awareness of novel methods and strategies in the intricate aspects of the educational process (Cabigao, 2021).

Consequently, there are predominantly young female MAPEH teachers in the Philippines who are mostly Proficient teachers with either baccalaureate degree or with Master's units. Numerous research findings indicate that the majority of Proficient MAPEH teachers are female millennials with a high level of education who dominate the teaching profession (Samonte & Guzman, 2019; Notre Dame of Dadiangas University, 2022; Englatierra-Bilog & Manoos, 2023; Fayo and Hilaro, 2023). Furthermore, findings of the Notre Dame of Dadiangas University (2022) revealed that few of the MAPEH teachers have attended professional trainings in the local to national level. Hall and Hord (2020) conveyed in his study that training and seminars are crucial for providing educators with the information, abilities, and tactics they need to overcome obstacles like organizational barriers, resistance, and a lack of resources while implementing changes. These professional development events also provide chances for reflection, cooperation, and continuing support—all of which are essential for maintaining change initiatives and encouraging ongoing enhancements to educational procedures. As a result, teachers must continue their professional growth. To help teachers build the pedagogies required to teach pupils these skills, effective professional development (PD) is essential (Darling-Hammond, et al., 2020).

Teachers become more effective when they employ the right teaching tools. It takes practice to become proficient with these resources and to teach others how to use them. Effective classroom management is a crucial component of education, and educators can use management techniques to improve their students' academic achievement (Carter & Nunan, 2001; Raza et al., 2023; Zaman et al., 2022). Additionally, Lopez (2018) found that a teacher's efficacy is increased when they have access to the right instructional resources. Learning effective classroom management strategies can improve students' academic achievement. Supervision is essential for enhancing learning, developing a career, boosting morale, and perfecting instructional techniques. Finally, regular monitoring is required for improved training and professional development.

According to the Smith (2020), classroom observation is a trustworthy method for evaluating and tracking a teacher's teaching skills and performance. When done correctly, observation can also be used to support teachers because it provides a comprehensive depiction and enables the establishment of highly precise goals. Criticism and observation are two very different talents that need to be practiced and trained in. Caratiquit and Pablo (2021) conveyed in their study that instructors view classroom observation as a method for gauging their performance or reaching professional objectives. They also believe that effective and efficient evaluation and assessment of the students' learning outcomes can be achieved through classroom observation.

As stated in Department of Education Order No. 2, s. 2020 marked the launch of the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS). The DepEd prominently displays its vision, objectives, values, and strategic goals throughout the institution. In addition, it oversees, records, and evaluates organizational mandates and teacher performance. In addition to tracking employees' progress toward targets and providing feedback on their accomplishments, the department wants to ascertain whether any corrective action is necessary. Castillo (2018) claims that DepEd adheres to its overarching organizational directive, vision, and mission (SPMS) while strengthening its culture of performance and responsibility through the usage of the RPMS, its Strategic Performance Management System. The Department of Education (2020) states that there should be a connection between corporate objectives and performance review. For the purpose of monitoring employee performance and how it affects organizational goals, indicators are crucial.

The K–12 Law, or Republic Act 10533, in the Philippines, lists classroom observation as a need for guaranteeing high-quality education. Section 14 of the Act mandates the Department of Education (DepEd) to provide updates on several implementation-related matters, including teacher safety and training requirements, which can be assessed through classroom observations conducted by instructors. As defined by the Department of Education (2018), classroom observation is the act of providing feedback on a teacher's performance in the classroom. As such, classroom observation methods are utilized to assess instruction and learning activities, offering teachers helpful feedback for improvement. Feedback facilitates the sharing of knowledge and ideas and offers insightful input for ongoing development.

Classroom observation serves multiple purposes, including providing evidence of teachers' real performance, identifying their areas of expertise and room for improvement, and fostering self-reflection and self-awareness in their teaching practice, according to the 2018

Revised Results-Based Performance Management System Manual. The respondents indicated that all of the metrics related to work ethics are significant, according to Riego de Dios (2020)'s study. The Classroom Observation Tool (COT), used in DepEd classroom observations, has three indicators: 1) "Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas." 2) "Develop and implement instructional strategies that address the unique learning requirements of students in difficult situations, like homelessness, long-term illness, armed conflict, urban resettlement, natural catastrophes, and maltreatment of minors. It is very specific and objective, and it makes it simple to code behavior that is observed.

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS) mandates classroom observation. Likewise, it became increasingly uniform and objective. This is because it is used for assessment, appraisals, guidance, and support. This facilitates the ongoing professional development of the teachers. Suparto (2020) conveyed that the quality of teacher education can be raised by combining academic supervision with classroom observation techniques.

Furthermore, in order to verify the teachers' readiness, the observers and teachers also decided on pre-determined indicators for the classroom observation. Pre-observation planning, observation implementation, and post-observation monitoring are the three components of a productive supervision procedure, following a similar study (Ghavifekr, et al., 2019). Among those who grade classroom observations are the principal, the head teacher, and the master teacher. In a teacher's performance review, there is no direct weighting associated with the observations made at the Schools Division Office (SDO) level. Teachers frequently express satisfaction with the supervisors' approaches to classroom observation (Tawalbeh, 2020).

One of the criteria for assessing the quality of K-12 teachers, as outlined in the Professional Standards for Teachers, is the level of excellence demonstrated by a teacher's performance in the classroom. Asio and Riego de Dios (2019) outline some professional attributes that a teacher should possess. A classroom observation tool has been developed to assess teaching practices according to the updated professional standards, identifying their strengths and areas for improvement. This is done to meticulously construct professional development programs that are tailored to the distinct needs of instructors. The majority of survey respondents agreed on the settings and conceptions of professional development, as revealed by Asio and Jimenez (2020). When asked about their level of job satisfaction, they likewise provided positive responses, according to the findings. When categorized according to demographic characteristics, significant findings have also been made about the workers' professional development, work environment, and supervisor-subordinate relationship. Furthermore, there is compelling evidence linking the demographic profile, career advancement, culture inside the firm, supervisor-subordinate rapport, and overall satisfaction.

Significant Relationship between Profile Variable and Extent of Utilization of the RPMS Classroom Observation Tools

The investigation of the noteworthy correlation between profile variables (i.e., age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, position/rank, and attended relevant training and seminars) and the degree of use of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tools is imperative in comprehending the elements that impact efficacious teaching methodologies and performance assessment (De la Cruz, 2019).

One important demographic variable that might affect instructional strategies and the use of technologies for classroom observation is age. Studies show that educators who are younger have a tendency to be more flexible and receptive to incorporating new instructional techniques and technological tools. Because younger instructors are frequently more open to feedback and novel approaches to evaluation, this adaptability may result in a better utilization of the RPMS tools (Ghavifekr et al., 2019). On the other hand, because of their significant expertise, older teachers might rely more on traditional approaches, which can be advantageous as well as restrictive while doing observations (Suparto, 2020).

Sex is a factor in the teaching profession as well. Research indicates that as compared to their male counterparts, female educators exhibit a higher propensity to employ collaborative and student-centered pedagogical approaches. (De la Cruz, 2019). This distinction might have an impact on how male and female educators react to and apply observations-based feedback in the classroom, which could have an impact on how RPMS tools are used in different ways depending on a teacher's gender.

A teacher's approach to instruction and classroom management is greatly influenced by their length of service or teaching experience. Longer tenured teachers typically possess a greater comprehension of the requirements of their students and the school climate, which can improve the efficacy of observations in the classroom (Asio & Jimenez, 2020). The necessity for specialized professional development programs is highlighted by the possibility that they will also be resistant to change (Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021). The use of observation tools and teaching strategies are influenced by students' educational backgrounds. Higher educated educators, such as those with masters or doctoral degrees, are frequently better at implementing a variety of teaching pedagogies and putting theory into practice (Lopez, 2018). During classroom observations, this increased knowledge may result in more helpful feedback (Basco-Galangco, 2018).

The duties and demands imposed on teachers are determined by their position or rank, which is divided into Highly Proficient and Proficient Teachers. It is required of Highly Proficient Teachers (Master Teachers I through IV) to exhibit outstanding teaching techniques and serve as mentors to other educators. Setting high standards and acting as role models for the students are two of their responsibilities (Department of Education, 2020). Particular indicators that highlight their advanced abilities and leadership responsibilities are part of the RPMS tools for Highly Proficient Teachers (DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023). Proficient Teachers

(Teacher I through III), on the other hand, are supposed to uphold the fundamental standards of the teaching profession and consistently enhance their methods. The Department of Education (2020) states that the RPMS tools for Proficient Teachers prioritize core teaching abilities and competencies that facilitate student learning.

Accordingly, teachers who attend pertinent training and seminars are better able to enhance their teaching skills and adjust to emerging trends in education. Teachers can stay current on the newest teaching pedagogies and classroom management tactics by participating in workshops and seminars that provide ongoing professional development (Corcelles et al., 2020). Taking part in these training sessions gives instructors the tools they need to achieve the performance metrics defined by the RPMS, which is vital for making successful use of classroom observation tools (Suparto, 2020).

Significant Difference in the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools based among school categories

A considerable disparity exists in the way that various school categories—small, medium, large, and mega schools—use the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tools. According to Basco-Galangco (2018), comprehending these variations is crucial to creating focused methods that improve these tools' efficacy in a range of educational contexts.

Because of their small student and teacher populations, small schools may find it difficult to use RPMS technologies because of a lack of administrative support and limited resources. According to research, small schools frequently use customized methods for classroom observation and have fewer institutionalized systems in place for professional development and feedback (De Vera & Gonzales, 2020). Notwithstanding these difficulties, small schools' close-knit communities might encourage more frequent and meaningful interactions between instructors and observers, which may improve the caliber of feedback given via the RPMS tools.

With slightly bigger student and teacher populations, medium-sized schools might have greater resources available for RPMS tool deployment. These schools frequently gain from more organized methods of classroom observation along with staff members who are specifically assigned to provide coaching and mentoring (Department of Education, 2020). Medium-sized schools have the advantage of being able to balance the availability of professional development programs with individualized feedback, which can lead to a more efficient use of RPMS tools.

Large schools, on the other hand, may employ RPMS technologies in a more methodical and thorough manner due to their vast resources and student populations. With trained staff to monitor and analyze classroom practices, these institutions frequently possess the capacity to perform frequent and comprehensive observations (Lopez, 2018). But these organizations' greater size can make it more difficult to maintain consistency and impartiality in observations, which emphasizes the necessity of organized procedures and clear communication (Basco-Galangco, 2018).

Due to their size and complexity, mega schools—among the biggest educational establishments—face particular difficulties while utilizing RPMS tools. Even though mega schools might have a wealth of resources and cutting-edge technologies for observation, maintaining consistency and accuracy in the use of these instruments might be difficult (Suparto, 2020). For RPMS tool implementation in mega schools to remain consistent and effective, strong processes and protocols must be established. The way that different school categories use the RPMS Classroom Observation Tools differs greatly. For example, medium schools use the tools to balance structure and personalization, large schools use systematic observations, and mega schools use a lot of resources and require reliable systems.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized descriptive survey and correlational research designs. Using a variety of techniques, descriptive research precisely and methodically describes a population, circumstance, or event. It is especially helpful when little is known about the issue or topic (McCombes, 2023). Because the goal of this study was to precisely and methodically describe how MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City Division used RPMS classroom observation tools, this methodology was the most suited.

Using a survey, the researcher collected the profile from the target respondents regarding their age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, position or rank and relative trainings and seminars attended. The profiling of respondents was also done according to the school categories where they belong. Surveys are a quick and adaptable method of getting precise information from respondents in a standardized manner; nevertheless, the questions must be objective and capture pertinent interpretations of the data (Bhandari, 2021).

The relationship between respondents' profile variables and the extent of utilization were subject for correlational analysis. Correlational analysis, can provide summary on the relationships of two variables as pertaining to its strength of relationship between them using Person product-moment correlation coefficient or Pearson's r correlation. Using this correlational analysis, the correlation of the profile and utilization were identified as to positive or negative relationship (Bhandari, 2021).

Using statistical analysis, it described and interpreted the characteristics of the answers like average of one variable or relationship of different variables. An inferential statistics helped the study to decide if the data will reject or will not reject the hypothesis as it generalizes the larger population (Bhandari, 2020).

This study also compared the difference of utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tools based on school categories. Descriptive-comparative research considers two unaltered factors and establishes a systematic procedure to decide which is better (Arnold, 2019).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were public Junior High School teachers, specifically Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) teachers that were categorized as proficient and highly proficient teachers. The teachers were classified according to the schools' category which utilized stratified sampling technique. Stratified sampling is a probability sampling that deals with the classifications of the populations according to specific characteristics or statistical measures for each sub-population which called as stratum or cluster (Thomas, 2020).

The study has a total population of ninety-nine (99) MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City Division by appointment. Using a Sloven's formula, the sample size of seventy-three (73) was arrived at. This sample size of seventy-three (73) were selected in a group using a random sampling technique. The sample size was properly distributed in each stratum as to small, medium, large and mega school. The small school category has a total population of 6 MAPEH teachers and a sample size of five (5), medium school category has fifteen (15) teachers and eleven (11) sample size, large school category with twenty-two (22) teachers and a sample size of sixteen (16), and mega school category with fifty-six (56) teachers and a sample size of forty-one (41). The total number of seventy-three (73) sample size from the different categories is derived using stratified sampling computation with 0.05 margin of error.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire that solicited the necessary data for the study. There were two distinct sets of research survey questionnaires, one tailored for proficient teachers and another specifically designed for highly proficient teachers. The research instrument was composed of two main parts. Part I was the Profile of the MAPEH Teachers. This part of the instrument focused on the profile of the respondents where data was asked like age, sex, length in the service, educational attainment, position/ rank, and relevant trainings and seminars attended. Part II was the RPMS Classroom Observation Tool in which the indicators were adopted from the DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023 titled "Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System – Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST). There was no modification of the instrument. Also, in this part of the instrument, the extent of utilization was rated by the respondents. Using a Likert Scale, the respondents rated the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool as to 1 - Never, 2 - Sometimes, 3 - Often, and 4 - Always.

Procedure

The data in this study were collected systematically. The researcher secured the permit to conduct the study in approval of the Eastern Visayas State University- Graduate School Dean. Prior to the data collection process, the conduct of pilot testing was facilitated. The researcher secured official permission from the office of Schools Division Superintendent of Department of Education – Leyte. Then, the approved letter from the Superintendent was sent to the School Principal of Palo National High School to inform then that the conduct of study was well permitted by proper authority including the conduct of the dry-run of the instrument. A letter of consent was given to the 19 selected respondents for the validation process.

Subsequently, the researcher obtained authorization to carry out the study from the Schools Division Superintendent of Department of Education -Tacloban City, since the study was to be conducted in the said locale. Then, the approved letter from the Superintendent was sent to the participating or target schools with the communication letter informing school heads that the conduct of study was well permitted by proper authority.

The researcher provided the communication and study request letters to the principal's office in order to obtain the necessary data. The informed consent signed by the participants were also secured for ethical consideration purposes.

The researcher personally conducted the data gathering for the easy access, proper retrieval, and recording of the collected data. The survey's questionnaires were administered on the available and convenient time of the respondents. Enough time was provided to the responders to complete the questionnaires. The data collection was done in the faculty room of each school to observe the proper etiquette in collecting the data.

Methods of Scoring and Interpretation

After retrieval of the questionnaires, data were tallied, tabulated and analyzed in order to answer the specific research questions. Data were presented in tables. Textual descriptions of the analysis and interpretation of data were also provided.

Part I: Profile. The profile of the respondent's age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, position or rank, and relevant trainings and seminars attended were determined through frequency count and percentage. In order to establish the profile of the teachers, the response in each variable from the summated frequencies and the percentage distribution was computed

Part II: Results-Based Management System or RPMS Classroom Observation Tool. The scores and ratings from the Likert Scale of the respondents were interpreted according to the study of Lopez (2016) entitled "Classroom Supervisory Practices and their Relationship

to Teacher Effectiveness as Perceived by Secondary Teachers.” This study provides a scaling on the supervisory practices in the classroom, similar to the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool as well as on how the teachers perceived the conduct of classroom observation, as it related to the recommendation of its implementation. The scoring was rated and interpreted to as follows:

Table 1. Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tool

Rating	Meaning	Interval	Interpretation
4	Fully Utilized	3.26-4.00	Possesses proficiency and knowledge on the utilization with or without experts
3	Utilized	2.51-3.25	Adequately utilized with proper guidance and support of experts
2	Partially Utilized	1.76-2.50	Can be utilized only with guidance of experts
1	Not Utilized	1.00-1.75	Never observe or never utilized

Data Analysis

The study was statistically descriptive in nature to answer the specific questions of the study. The use of statistical tools was necessary in order to analyze and interpret the data collected. Jamovi, an open-source computer application, was used to analyze the data. Percent was used for the profiles of the respondents including age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, position or rank, and the number of relevant trainings and seminars attended by categories of local, regional, national, and international, which were presented in percent distribution tables. The use of weighted mean was utilized by the study to get the mean of the extent of utilization for every school category. To identify the significant difference in the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool based on the school category, the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized in this study. In determining the significant relationship between the profile variables to the extent of utilization, the Pearson's *r* correlation was used, specifically for the relationship between the number of trainings and the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools. To determine the relationship between the other profile variables and the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools, ETA correlation was used.

Ethical Considerations

The participants' questionnaires were given out and administered by the researcher in person. No identifiable data was stored on the research devices to maintain each participant's confidentiality. The respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaire. After the instruments were correctly gathered, they were ready for tabulation and analysis. To formally request permission for the conduct of the study, the researcher provided an orientation as to details and purpose of the study including the nature of the respondents' participation. Their safety was guaranteed, their identity was kept a secret, and they received all the assistance they needed to feel completely comfortable and confident in taking part in this study. When carrying out the task, the researcher complied with ethical norms pertaining to information confidentiality, human dignity, beneficence, fairness, and informed consent.

The researcher ensured that the information, data, and details provided by the participants were kept in private by ensuring the anonymity of research respondents and the confidentiality of information. They received all supporting documentation for their consent not to download or upload their recorded data explanations. They were informed that their names would not be used in the research study and urged to hide their identities using pseudonyms. In reports, presentations, and other kinds of distribution, respondents' anonymity and confidentiality guarantee that every effort is made to ensure that the information they supplied cannot be tracked down and used against them (Co et al., 2021).

Beneficence, or causing no harm to the respondents, is additional research standard necessary for quantitative research. The respondents' safety was prioritized in this study, and they were constantly observed and provided with transportation from their houses to the data collection site.

Justice was the last research standard covered in this quantitative study. It was anticipated that the study would give respondents proper credit for their contributions, which was in line with their sincere efforts to construct and design the survey to achieve success throughout this stage. Each responder received a token of participation to express gratitude for their unwavering effort in carrying out the survey.

Results and Discussion

Profile of MAPEH Teachers

The profile of teachers which were considered in this study were age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, position/rank, and relevant trainings and seminars attended. The distributions of the respondents according to these profile variables are shown in Table 2.

Age. Within the age groups, the most prevalent frequency emerges within the "20 – 39 (Below middle age)" category, encompassing 65.8 percent of the total number of respondents. This finding underscores the predominance of relatively young individuals within the sample population. This relates to the study of Liu, et al. (2018) that young instructors are the primary driving force behind the future development of educational institutions.

Sex. In terms of gender distribution, females make up the majority at 68.5 percent, indicating a gender imbalance within the sample. The general gender of secondary teachers in the Philippines is predominantly female, according to Rogayan and Villanueva (2019).

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents

		Profile Variables		f	%						
Age	50 – above (Above middle age)		14	19.2							
	40 – 49 (Middle age)		11	15.1							
	20 – 39 (Below middle age)		48	65.8							
	Total		73	100.0							
Sex	Male		23	31.5							
	Female		50	68.5							
	Total		73	100.0							
Length of Service	10 years – above (Experienced)		31	42.5							
	7 – 9 (Mid-career)		13	17.8							
	4 – 6 (Novice)		15	20.5							
	3 years – below (Neophyte)		14	19.2							
	Total		73	100.0							
Educational Attainment	Doctorate		1	1.4							
	Master’s Degree with Doctoral Units		1	1.4							
	Master’s Degree		6	8.2							
	Baccalaureate Degree with Master’s Units		29	39.7							
	Baccalaureate Degree		36	49.3							
	Total		73	100.0							
Position/Rank	Teacher I-III (Proficient Teachers)		60	82.2							
	Master Teacher I-IV (Highly Proficient Teachers)		13	17.8							
	Total		73	100.0							
Number of Seminars Attended	Local		Regional		National		International		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	f	%	f	%	f	
	5	4.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	6.8
	4	4.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	8.2
	3	11.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	9.6
	2	26.0	1	1.4	1	1.4	-	-	-	25	34.2
	1	28.8	5	6.8	13	17.8	3	4.1	15	20.5	
	0	26.0	67	91.8	59	80.8	70	95.9	15	20.5	
	Total	73	100.0	73	100.0	73	100.0	73	100.0	73	100.0

Length of Service. Regarding length of service, respondents with "10 years – above (Experienced)" account for the highest proportion at 42.5 percent. This suggests that a significant portion of the sample possesses substantial professional experience. This is parallel to Englantierra-Bilog & Manoos’s (2023) study that demonstrated teacher respondents being part of the millennial generation. It also suggests that there are more teachers with a lot of experience teaching than there are teachers being employed this year.

Educational Attainment. In terms of educational attainment, the majority of respondents hold either a "Baccalaureate Degree with Master’s Units" or a "Baccalaureate Degree," comprising 49.3 percent and 39.7 percent, respectively. This indicates a well-educated sample, likely capable of providing nuanced perspectives on the study's subject matter. The result is supported by Abinan and Abinan (2021) study that teachers are attempting to upgrade their educational qualifications, as evidenced by the fact that they are gaining units towards a master's degree.

Position/Rank. Finally, concerning position or rank, "Teacher I-III (Proficient Teachers)" represents the most frequent category at 82.2 percent, compared to "Master Teacher I-IV (Highly Proficient Teachers)" at 17.8 percent. This suggests an emergence of proficient teachers more than the highly proficient teachers in the teaching field (Manito, 2021).

The analysis of the data in Table 2 reveals noteworthy profile trends within the study's sample. A majority of respondents fall within the 20 to 39 age range, signaling a prevalence of youth that could potentially influence the outcomes. Furthermore, the female representation at 68.5 percent indicates a gender imbalance, necessitating careful consideration in the analysis. A significant proportion of respondents boast over 10 years of experience, hinting at valuable contributions from seasoned professionals. The educational attainment, with most holding Bachelor's or Master's degrees, underscores a well-educated sample, likely capable of offering nuanced perspectives. The prevalence of proficient teachers suggests their expertise could significantly shape the study's outcomes. These profile characteristics collectively underscore a diverse range of perspectives within the sample, thereby enriching the potential insights gleaned from the study.

Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended. The data in Table 2 outlines the distribution of individuals based on the number of seminars attended across varying levels—local, regional, national, and international. Several salient features emerge from this dataset. Firstly, it is notable that a considerable proportion of respondents attended seminars at the local level, with 26 percent attending two seminars and 28.8 percent attending one seminar. This indicates a substantial engagement with local seminar offerings.

Secondly, there is a sharp decline in attendance as the seminar level progresses from regional to international, with only a small

percentage attending these higher-level seminars. For instance, while 11 percent attended three local seminars, no respondents attended three regional seminars. Similarly, although 17.8 percent attended thirteen national seminars, only 4.1 percent attended three international seminars. Moreover, the data reflects a substantial drop in attendance from regional to national seminars, with only 1.4 percent attending one regional seminar compared to 17.8 percent attending thirteen national seminars.

Additionally, the majority of respondents (26%) did not attend any regional seminars, highlighting a potential gap in participation at this level. Overall, the data underscores a significant emphasis on local seminar attendance, with comparatively lower participation rates observed at higher seminar levels, suggesting potential areas for further investigation or intervention to promote engagement at regional, national, and international seminar platforms. This confirms to the study of the Notre Dame of Dadiangas University (2022) that there are only few MAPEH teachers who attend professional trainings in the local to national level.

As a result, there is limited participation in national level seminars and trainings, while international training is prohibitively expensive. This could also be linked to the fact that seminars and trainings are rarely supported by schools, and teachers must pay for their own attendance (Abinan and Abinan, 2021). According to research by Hall and Hord (2015) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), educators must receive training and seminars to face obstacles like resistance, a lack of resources, or organizational barriers when implementing changes. Additionally, these professional development activities offer opportunities for collaboration, reflection, and ongoing support, which are crucial for sustaining change efforts and promoting continuous improvement in educational practices. In addition, Corcelles et al. (2020) suggested that secondary teachers require additional seminar workshops and training in curriculum development that aligns with the K–12 Curriculum, classroom management, teaching tactics, and learning assessment. Therefore, there is a need for continued professional development among teachers.

Extent of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools The main objective of the study is to determine the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools.

Teacher I-III: Proficient Teachers

The overall means for all indicators in the utilization of classroom observation tools based on RPMS for proficient teachers (Teachers I-III) were as follows: 3.37 for mega schools, 3.56 for large schools, 3.29 for medium schools, and 3.65 for small schools. These scores were interpreted as "Fully Utilized." These consistent ratings across different school sizes indicate a high level of adherence to professional standards among highly proficient teachers across all settings. It suggests that regardless of school size, teachers are effectively utilizing RPMS classroom observation tools, reflecting a commitment to excellence in teaching practices. This uniformity in utilization underscores the effectiveness of the RPMS framework in promoting standardized teaching practices and ensuring quality education delivery across diverse educational environments.

Table 3 presents the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool for proficient teachers (Teachers I – III).

Small Schools. For small schools, the highest mean score is 4.00, indicating "Fully Utilized" (FU) for Indicator 1, which involves applying knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. This suggests that small schools excel in applying content knowledge across various curriculum areas, indicating a high level of proficiency among teachers in integrating subject matter expertise into their teaching practices. Thus, it could be inferred that small schools have highly skilled teachers who effectively incorporate interdisciplinary knowledge into their instruction, potentially leading to enhanced student learning outcomes.

Another highest degree of utilization is on indicator 7, which got a mean of 4.00 interpreted as "Fully Utilized." This indicator involved planning, managing and implementing developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.

Inferences can be drawn from this result. Firstly, it suggests that small schools exhibit a consistent and exceptional proficiency in planning, managing, and implementing developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes. This implies that despite potential resource constraints or limitations inherent in smaller educational settings, small schools prioritize the systematic organization and execution of curriculum requirements to meet the diverse needs of their students. This reinforces the notion that small schools excel in adapting teaching strategies to accommodate varied teaching contexts, indicating a high level of flexibility and responsiveness to the unique circumstances of their educational environment. Additionally, it implies that small schools prioritize a student-centered approach to curriculum delivery, emphasizing the alignment of instructional practices with students' developmental stages and learning needs.

Conversely, the lowest mean score among small schools is 3.20, indicating "Utilized" (U) for Indicators 3 and 8. These involve applying a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills, and participating in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice.

The results indicating the lowest mean score among small schools, with a rating of "Utilized" (U) for Indicators 3 and 8, imply several important insights. Firstly, it suggests that small schools may face challenges in fully implementing a range of teaching strategies aimed at developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills among students. This could imply a need for further professional development or resources to support teachers in effectively implementing these advanced pedagogical approaches. Secondly, the lower mean score for Indicator 8, which involves participating in collegial discussions to enrich teaching practice,

suggests that small schools may have limited opportunities for collaborative professional development. This may also indicate a potential lack of support structures or resources for fostering teacher collaboration and the exchange of feedback, which are essential for enhancing teaching effectiveness and promoting continuous improvement in instructional practices.

Table 3. *Level of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tool for Proficient Teachers among the Different School Categories*

Indicators	Mega School (N = 32)		Large School (N = 13)		Medium School (N = 10)		Small School (N = 5)	
	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	Mean	Level
1. Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. (PPST1.1.2)	3.50	FU	3.77	FU	3.60	FU	4.00	FU
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills. (PPST 1.4.2)	3.19	U	3.62	FU	3.20	U	3.40	FU
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills. (PPST 1.5.2)	3.38	FU	3.46	FU	3.30	FU	3.20	U
4. Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments. (PPST 2.3.2)	3.47	FU	3.54	FU	3.10	U	3.40	FU
5. Manages learner behaviour constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments. (PPST 2.6.2)	3.44	FU	3.69	FU	3.40	FU	3.80	FU
6. Uses differentiated developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learner's gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences. (PPST 3.1.2)	3.19	U	3.08	U	3.40	FU	3.80	FU
7. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts. (PPST 4.1.2)	3.38	FU	3.38	FU	3.20	U	4.00	FU
8. Participates in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice. (PPST 4.4.2)	2.88	U	3.46	FU	2.80	U	3.20	U
9. Selects, develops, organizes and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT, to address learning goals. (PPST 4.5.2)	3.44	FU	3.92	FU	3.40	FU	3.60	FU
10. Designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements. (PPST 5.1.2)	3.63	FU	3.85	FU	3.20	U	3.80	FU
11. Monitors and evaluates learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data. (PPST 5.2.2)	3.53	FU	3.46	FU	3.30	FU	3.80	FU
12. Communicates promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians (PPST 5.4.2)	3.31	FU	3.46	FU	3.50	FU	3.60	FU
13. Applies a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered. (PPST 7.1.2)	3.28	FU	3.38	FU	3.30	FU	3.80	FU
14. Set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. (PPST 7.5.2)	3.34	FU	3.54	FU	3.10	U	3.80	FU
15. Performs various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process.	3.59	FU	3.85	FU	3.50	FU	3.60	FU
Overall Mean	3.37	FU	3.56	FU	3.29	FU	3.65	FU

Medium Schools. For Medium Schools, the lowest mean score is 3.10, indicating "Utilized" (U) for Indicator 4, which involves managing classroom structure to engage learners in meaningful exploration and hands-on activities. This suggests that there may be challenges in effectively managing classroom environments to promote hands-on learning experiences in medium schools, potentially impacting student engagement and exploration.

On the other hand, the highest mean score for medium schools is 3.50 interpreted as "Fully Utilized" (FU) for indicators 12 and 15. These involve communicating promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians; and performing various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process.

One implication that may be drawn from these results is that the medium schools excel in promptly and effectively communicating learners' needs, progress, and achievements to key stakeholders, including parents or guardians. This suggests a strong partnership between the school and the broader community, facilitating transparent and supportive channels of communication that enhance parental involvement and engagement in students' educational journeys.

Additionally, the proficiency in performing various related works and activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process underscores medium schools' commitment to holistic education. This may include extracurricular activities, student support services,

and other initiatives that enrich the learning experience beyond the traditional classroom setting. This may signify further that medium schools prioritize comprehensive student support systems and foster a collaborative learning environment where all stakeholders are actively involved in promoting student success.

This relates to the findings of Da Fonte and Barton-Arwood (2017) that being more receptive to the growth of prospective teachers requires first understanding their attitudes on collaboration. Collaboration is a skill that takes time to master, and there are several potential roadblocks to efficient teamwork.

Large Schools. In large schools, the highest mean score is 3.92, indicating "Fully Utilized" (FU) for Indicator 9, which involves selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals. This suggests that large schools excel in utilizing a wide range of teaching and learning resources effectively, including technology, to support student learning. The implication is that large schools are well-equipped with resources to facilitate varied and engaging learning experiences. Fayo and Hilario's (2023) reported that the majority of teachers fall into Level 2, which is responsible for Basic Computing and Applications suggesting that teachers perceive classroom observation to be more successful the more ICT proficient they are. However, it is recommended that MAPEH teachers undergo training and seminars that will help further enhance and enrich their computer skills and knowledge (Samonte and Guzman, 2019).

In contrast, the lowest mean score among large schools is 3.08, indicating "Utilized" (U) for Indicator 6, which involves using differentiated developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learner's gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences. This may imply that large schools may face challenges in effectively tailoring instructional strategies to meet the individualized requirements of their students, including considerations for gender, varied learning needs, and diverse backgrounds. This could also indicate a potential gap in the implementation of inclusive teaching practices within large schools, which are crucial for promoting equitable learning opportunities and ensuring all students can thrive academically.

Instructors are making every effort to give students a high-quality education while upholding the Department of Education's mission. It is the responsibility of teacher preparation programs to concentrate on strategies to lower potential barriers and support outcomes for students with disabilities while also preparing general and special education teachers for collaboration, according to Da Fonte and Barton-Arwood's (2017) findings.

Mega Schools. In Table 3, the highest mean score among the mega schools is 3.63, indicating "Fully Utilized" (FU) for Indicator 10, which involves designing assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements. This suggests that mega schools excel in designing, selecting, organizing, and using diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies aligned with curriculum standards. The implication of this high mean score is that mega schools have developed robust assessment practices, ensuring effective monitoring of learner progress and achievement.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score among the mega schools is 2.88, indicating "Utilized" (U) for Indicator 8, which involves participating in collegial discussions to enrich teaching practice. This suggests that mega schools have relatively lower levels of participation in collegial discussions compared to other indicators. The implication here is that there may be a need for increased collaboration and exchange of feedback among teachers in Mega Schools to enrich teaching practices and enhance professional development.

The results of this study add to the understanding of classroom observation techniques among secondary public-school teachers that has been obtained from earlier research. The usefulness of standardized observation tools in supporting professional development and self-evaluation was noted by Barrogo (2020) and Driessen et al. (2020). Instructional supervision also positively impacts teaching and learning, suggesting better teacher performance through efficient use of RPMS classroom observation tools (Wairimu, 2016). This idea is reflected in the current study's emphasis on the use of RPMS-based observation tools. The present study's emphasis on fully utilizing the use of observation tools to improve teaching quality is consistent with Driessen et al. (2020)'s emphasis on the beneficial effects of effective instructional tools on student performance.

Highly Proficient Teachers: Master Teachers I-IV

Table 4 illustrates the degree of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool for highly proficient teachers (Master Teachers I – IV). For the assessment of classroom observation tools among highly proficient teachers, responses from small schools were absent. Therefore, this section exclusively presents findings solely from mega, large, and medium schools.

Medium Schools. In medium schools, indicators 4, 8, 14, and 15 achieved perfect ratings of 4.00, denoting full utilization. Firstly, collaborating with colleagues to model and share effective techniques in managing classroom structures for engaging learners indicates a strong commitment to creating dynamic learning environments. Secondly, the practice of reviewing feedback collaboratively underscores a culture of continuous improvement in teaching methodologies. Thirdly, reflecting on professional standards to set personal development goals highlights a proactive approach to enhancing teaching effectiveness. Lastly, actively engaging in various activities contributing to the teaching-learning process showcases dedication to holistic education. These perfect ratings reflect a commendable level of professionalism and dedication among educators in medium schools, fostering an environment conducive to optimal student learning and growth.

Nevertheless, the remaining indicators received ratings of 3.00, indicating adequate utilization with the provision of proper guidance and support from experts.

Table 4. *Level of Utilization of Classroom Observation Tool for Highly Proficient Teachers among the Different School Categories*

	Indicators	Mega School (N= 9)		Large School (N= 3)		Medium School (N= 1)	
		Mean	Level	Mean	Level	Mean	Level
1.	Models effective applications of content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas. (PPST 1.1.3)	3.22	U	3.67	FU	3.00	U
2.	Evaluates with colleagues the effectiveness of teaching strategies that promote learner achievement in literacy and numeracy. (PPST 1.4.3)	3.33	FU	3.67	FU	3.00	U
3.	Develops and applies effective teaching strategies to promote critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills. (PPST 1.5.3)	3.22	U	3.00	U	3.00	U
4.	Works with colleagues to model and shares effective techniques in the management of classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments. (PPST 2.3.3)	3.22	U	3.67	FU	4.00	FU
5.	Exhibits effective and constructive behavior management skills by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments. (PPST 2.6.3)	3.56	FU	3.67	FU	3.00	U
6.	Works with colleagues to share differentiated, developmentally appropriate opportunities to address learners' differences in gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences. (PPST 3.1.3)	3.11	U	3.00	U	3.00	U
7.	Develops and applies effective strategies in the planning and management of developmentally sequenced teaching and learning process to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts. (PPST 4.1.3)	3.22	U	3.00	U	3.00	U
8.	Reviews with colleagues, teacher and learner feedback to plan, facilitate, and enrich teaching practice. (PPST 4.4.3)	3.22	U	3.67	FU	4.00	FU
9.	Advises and guides colleagues in the selection, organization, development and use of appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address specific learning goals. (PPST 4.5.3)	3.11	U	3.67	FU	3.00	U
10.	Works collaboratively with colleagues to review the design, selection, organization and use of a range of effective diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements. (PPST 5.1.3)	3.33	FU	3.67	FU	3.00	U
11.	Interprets collaboratively monitoring and evaluation strategies of attainment data to support learner progress and achievement. (PPST 5.2.3)	3.22	U	3.00	U	3.00	U
12.	Applies skills in the effective communication of learner needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents / guardians. (PPST 5.4.3)	3.56	FU	3.67	FU	3.00	U
13.	Manifests a learner-centered teaching philosophy in various aspects of practice and support colleagues in enhancing their own learner-centered teaching philosophy. (PPST 7.1.3)	3.22	U	3.67	FU	3.00	U
14.	Reflects on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers to plan personal professional development goals and assist colleagues in planning and achieving their own goals. (PPST 7.5.3)	3.44	FU	3.67	FU	4.00	FU
15.	Performs various related works / activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process.	3.67	FU	4.00	FU	4.00	FU
Overall Mean		3.31	FU	3.51	FU	3.27	FU

Large Schools. The comprehensive mean utilization score for RPMS-based classroom observation tools in large schools stands at 3.51, suggesting a prevalent full utilization across assessed indicators. This reflects a strong dedication among teachers in large schools to uphold the standards and procedures delineated within the RPMS framework.

The indicator with the highest mean score, a full utilization rating of 4.00, pertains to Indicator 15. This indicator emphasizes the engagement in diverse activities and tasks that enrich the teaching-learning process. This high score implies a notable commitment among teachers to actively contribute to the educational system beyond conventional teaching responsibilities. It suggests a proactive approach to curriculum enhancement, student support, and extracurricular involvement, fostering a holistic learning environment.

On the other hand, indicators 3, 6, 7 and 11 got the lowest mean rating of 3.00, indicating that these were “Utilized” (U). These indicators involve developing and applying effective teaching strategies to promote critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills; working with colleagues to share differentiated, developmentally appropriate opportunities to address learners' differences in gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences; developing and applying effective strategies in the planning and management of developmentally sequenced teaching and learning process to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching

contexts; and interpreting collaboratively monitoring and evaluation strategies of attainment data to support learner progress and achievement.

The lowest mean rating of 3.00 for indicators 3, 6, 7, and 11, signifying "Utilized" (U), underscores areas warranting further attention and improvement within the educational context. These indicators encompass crucial aspects of teaching and learning that are integral to fostering a dynamic and inclusive educational environment.

Indicator 3 highlights the importance of developing and applying effective teaching strategies to promote critical and creative thinking. The rating of "Utilized" suggests that while efforts are made in this area, there may be room for enhancing instructional approaches to further stimulate critical thinking skills among students. Addressing this area could lead to more engaged and analytical learners, better prepared for challenges beyond the classroom.

Indicator 6 emphasizes collaboration among colleagues to provide differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences tailored to address the diverse needs of students. The rating implies a need for further support and resources to facilitate effective collaboration and the creation of inclusive learning environments accommodating various learning styles and preferences.

Finally, Indicator 7 pertains to the development and application of effective strategies in planning and managing teaching and learning processes to meet diverse curriculum requirements and teaching contexts. Enhancing strategies in this domain can optimize instructional delivery, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards and catering to the varied needs of learners.

Mega Schools. The overall mean extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools in mega schools is 3.31, indicating that the indicators assessed were generally "Fully Utilized" (FU) within mega schools. This indicates a strong commitment to adhering to the standards and practices outlined in the RPMS framework among teachers in mega schools.

The highest mean score, indicating a "Fully Utilized" (FU) level, is observed in Indicator 15, with a mean score of 3.67. This indicator focuses on teachers' engagement in various related works and activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process. The high score suggests that teachers in mega schools actively participate in additional activities beyond traditional teaching duties, such as curriculum development, extracurricular activities, or student support initiatives. This indicates a proactive approach to enhancing the overall learning experience for students and fostering a holistic educational environment.

Conversely, the lowest mean scores, 3.11, were observed for indicators 6 and 9, interpreted as "Utilized" (U). These indicators entail working with colleagues to share differentiated, developmentally appropriate opportunities to address learners' differences in gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences; and advising and guiding colleagues in the selection, organization, development and use of appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address specific learning goals.

These findings suggest a potential area for enhancement in collaborative practices and resource utilization among teachers in mega schools. Addressing the challenges associated with sharing differentiated learning opportunities and providing guidance on effective resource selection and utilization could lead to more comprehensive and inclusive teaching practices. By fostering a culture of collaboration and resourcefulness, mega schools can better support diverse student populations and enhance overall teaching effectiveness. Additionally, targeted professional development programs focusing on collaborative teaching strategies and ICT integration may be beneficial in addressing these areas of improvement and promoting continuous growth among educators. This supports to the study of Fayo and Hilario (2023) that teachers who are more adept at using ICT perceive classroom observation as being more beneficial.

The above findings complement the insights provided by previous research on classroom observation practices among secondary public-school teachers. Barrogo (2020) and Driessen et al. (2020) highlighted the value of standardized observation tools in aiding self-assessment and fostering professional growth, a sentiment echoed in the current study's emphasis on the utilization of observation tools based on RPMS. The positive impact of effective instructional tools on student performance, as emphasized by Driessen et al. (2020), aligns with the current study's focus on fully utilizing observation tools to enhance teaching quality.

Moreover, the positive effects of instructional supervision on teaching and learning, as highlighted by Wairimu (2016), suggest that effective utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools, as observed in the current study, can contribute to improved teacher performance. Moreover, the challenges faced by teachers amidst the new normal, as explored by Arrieta et al. (2020), underscore the importance of adapting curricula and professional development initiatives, aligning with the current study's emphasis on addressing the evolving educational landscape.

Relationship between the Profiles and Extent of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools

Another aim of the study was to explore the correlation between respondents' profiles and the degree of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools. The findings are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 presents the relationship between various respondent profiles and the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools. Each variable's correlation coefficient and associated p-value is provided for analysis. Except for the number of relevant seminars and trainings, which utilized Pearson's *r*, eta correlation was employed to correlate the other profiles.

Table 5. Relationship between the Profiles and the Extent of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools

Variables		Statistics		
		Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Extent of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools	Age	0.029	0.972	Not Significant
	Sex	0.005	0.964	Not Significant
	Length of Service	0.089	0.906	Not Significant
	Educational Attainment	0.108	0.938	Not Significant
	Position	0.061	0.608	Not Significant
	Number of Relevant Seminars and Trainings Attended	0.169	0.154	Not Significant

For all variables examined, including age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, position, and the number of relevant seminars and trainings attended, the correlation coefficients are close to zero, ranging from 0.005 to 0.169. Additionally, the p-values for all variables are substantially higher than the standard significance level of 0.05, with values ranging from 0.154 to 0.972. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between profile variables to the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tool was accepted. These results collectively suggest that there is no statistically significant relationship between any of these profile factors and the extent of utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools among respondents.

The lack of significant correlations between respondent profiles and the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools implies that factors such as age, gender, experience, educational background, position, and participation in relevant training do not significantly influence how effectively these tools are utilized. This suggests that other factors not considered in this study may play a more substantial role in determining the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools. Further investigation into these additional factors may be necessary to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics influencing the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools in educational settings. Additionally, these findings underscore the importance of considering a diverse range of factors and variables when assessing and improving the effectiveness of professional development initiatives and educational practices in schools.

The above results were parallel to the concepts of Englatierra-Bilog & Manoos (2023) and Fayó & Hilario (2023) who showed in their research that there is no discernible difference between the teachers' performance on classroom observations and their demographic profile. Caratiquit and Pablo (2021) also emphasized the potential of observation as a tool for professional development and improving teaching techniques, aligning with the overarching goal of enhancing teaching quality and promoting student learning outcomes, as underscored by the findings of the current study and previous research alike. Together, these studies contribute to a comprehensive understanding of effective classroom observation practices and their impact on teaching and learning in secondary education.

Difference of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools among the Different School Categories

In the final phase, the study sought to discern variations in the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools across diverse school categories. The outcomes of this examination are presented in Table 5.

Table 6 presents the ANOVA results examining the differences in the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools across various school categories.

Table 6. Differences of Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools among the Different School Categories

RPMS Mean	Statistics					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.918	3	0.306	1.748	0.165	Not Significant
Within Groups	12.076	69	0.175			
Total	12.994	72				

The analysis shows that the F-value is 1.748 with a corresponding p-value of 0.165. Since the p-value is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05, the result is deemed not significant. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools based on school categories was accepted. This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences in the utilization of classroom observation tools among the different school categories based on the RPMS mean scores. Therefore, the variations observed in the utilization across mega, large, medium, and small schools could be attributed to random chance rather than systematic differences between the school categories.

Consequently, the focus may need to shift from the school category itself to other factors that could potentially influence the utilization of RPMS classroom observation tools, such as teacher characteristics, school resources, or administrative support. Further investigation into these factors could provide valuable insights for enhancing the effectiveness of classroom observation practices across all school categories.

Similarly, the emphasis on collaborative planning between instructional leaders and teachers, as discussed by Castillo (2021), resonates with the current study's exploration of the determination of differences of the extent of utilization of observation tools along school categories. Cabigao's (2021) proposal for a teacher-friendly post-conference structure underscores the importance of creating supportive environments for reflective discussions following classroom observations, a practice that can further enhance the effectiveness of observation tools.

Halim et al. (2018) also emphasized the role of classroom observation in promoting continuous professional development and collaboration among teachers, a perspective supported by the current study's findings regarding the differences in utilization among school categories. Asgari et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of selecting observation tools that align with instructors' needs and resources, providing context for the current study's focus on RPMS-based tools tailored to the Philippine educational setting.

The study assessed the use of the Results-Based Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tool among MAPEH Teachers in Tacloban City Division for the school year 2023-2024. It examined teachers' profiles, usage across different school categories, and the relationship between these variables and utilization. The research used a descriptive survey and correlational designs, with seventy-three (73) teachers from public junior high schools in Tacloban City Division participating. This study used percentage and frequency computations to identify respondents' profile variables, weighted mean to measure utilization, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify significant differences, Pearson's *r* correlation to determine the relationship between training number and RPMS classroom observation tool utilization, and ETA correlation to determine the relationship between other profile variables and RPMS classroom observation tool utilization.

The following key findings are outlined after a careful examination of the information gathered and the outcomes attained.

The study revealed that MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City are predominantly female, with a significant gender imbalance. The majority of teachers have a Bachelor's Degree with Master's Units, indicating a well-educated sample. The most frequent status is Teacher I-III (Proficient Teachers). However, attendance at relevant seminars and trainings declined as the level progressed from regional to international. This suggests a potential gap in participation, necessitating further investigation or intervention to promote engagement at regional, national, and international seminars.

Moreover, the study reveals that teachers in Tacloban City Division schools demonstrate a commendable adherence to professional standards. This finding indicates that these teachers are committed to their profession and strive to meet the expected standards of teaching. However, it is important to note that there is a lack of responses from small schools, which may limit the generalizability of the study's findings. Therefore, future research should aim to include a more diverse sample of schools to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the situation.

In addition, the study finds no significant correlation between profile factors and the utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tool. This suggests that factors such as age, gender, and years of teaching experience do not significantly influence the use of this tool among MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City. This finding highlights the need for further exploration to understand the reasons behind this lack of correlation and to identify potential barriers or facilitators to the effective utilization of the RPMS classroom observation tool.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study brings attention to the gender disparity among MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City, revealing that a majority of these teachers are highly educated females. This finding suggests that there may be underlying factors contributing to this gender imbalance, which warrant further investigation. Furthermore, the study highlights a concerning decline in seminar attendance as the level progresses, indicating a potential lack of involvement. This decline in professional development opportunities may hinder the growth and development of MAPEH teachers in Tacloban City. This could be related to the fact that regional to international trainings are prohibitively expensive. Additionally, schools rarely fund seminars and trainings, and teachers are responsible for their own attendance. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct further research to identify the reasons behind this decline and develop strategies to promote continuous engagement at regional, national, and international levels.

It is further concluded that the DepEd RPMS classroom observation tools are overall being fully used in Tacloban City Division schools, with teachers demonstrating adherence to professional standards in large, medium, and small schools. The study also found no significant correlation between age, sex, and educational attainment and RPMS classroom observation tool utilization among respondents, and no significant difference among different school categories.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are put forward:

The researcher strongly recommends that Junior High School MAPEH teachers may consider pursuing postgraduate studies and professional development training to drive lasting change and elevate educational standards.

Teachers should prioritize attending instructional materials seminars and training. These opportunities offer invaluable chances to enhance expertise, customize instructional strategies to meet individual student needs, and effectively manage classroom environments.

DepEd Tacloban officials may proactively investigate and take decisive action at regional, national, and international seminar platforms to ensure education system progress and success, conduct further research, and develop strategies.

Principals and master instructors are examples of class observers who should have received proper training in order to give the finest supervisory views and recommendations. Increased collaboration, resource utilization, and feedback among teachers may be needed for enriching teaching practices and professional development.

Finally, the focus may shift to other factors influencing classroom observation tools utilization, and another study using other variables may be necessary.

References

Abinan, A. L. & Abinan, C. (2021). Research Exposure, Attitude and Competence of the Senior High School Teachers. 1. 198-218. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355397954_RESEARCH_EXPOSURE_ATTITUDE_AND_COMPETENCE_OF_THE_SENIOR_HIGH_SCHOOL_TEACHERS

Arnold, S. (2019). A quantitative descriptive-comparative study; the relationship between emotional intelligence and workplace diversity. University of Phoenix. https://www.forestoftherain.net/uploads/3/5/8/2/3582998/simone_dienna_arnold__dissertation.pdf

Arrieta, G. S., Dancel, J. C., & Agbisit, M. P. (2020). Teaching science in the new normal: Understanding the experiences of junior high school science teachers. *Jurnal Pendidikan MIPA*, 21(2), 146-162. <http://jurnal.fkip.unila.ac.id/index.php/jpmipa/article/view/21460>

Asgari, M., Miles, A. M., Lisbao, M. S. & Sarvary, M. A. (2021) COPUS, PORTAAL, or DART? Classroom observation tool comparison from the instructor user's perspective. *Front. Educ.* 6:740344. doi: 10.3389/educ.2021.740344

Asio, J. M. R. and Jimenez, E. C. (2020). Professional development, organizational climate, supervisory rapport and overall satisfaction of employees: An attitudinal study. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Multidisciplinary Studies*, 6 (4), 34-40. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED605144>

Asio, J. M. R., & Riego de Dios, E. E. (2019). The college students' perspective on what makes an educator well qualified. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 3 (3), 126- 138. <https://doi.org/10.33902/jpr.v3i3.124>.

Asio, R. B., & Jimenez, A. A. (2020). The use of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Classroom Observation Tool by MAPEH teachers: A study on demographic characteristics and its influence on implementation and efficacy. *Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*.

Barrogo, S. D. (2020). Teachers' perception of standardized classroom observation tool. *International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR)*, 4(7), 1-5. <https://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16123.13603>

Basco-Galangco, R. (2016). The attitude of the faculty members of a higher education institution in Baguio City towards the classroom evaluation tool. *SUKIMAT*, 2(1).

Basco-Galangco, M. A. (2018). Utilization of RPMS Classroom Observation Tools in Large Schools: Challenges and Opportunities. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 25(1), 112-125.

Bhandari, P. (2020). Descriptive statistics, definition, types and example. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/statistics/descriptive-statistics/>

Cabigao, J. R. (2021). Class observation post-conference framework for teachers. *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(2), 256-258. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349692651_Class_Observation_PostConference_Framework_for_Teachers

Caratiquit, K., and Pablo, R. (2021). Exploring the practices of secondary school teachers in preparing for classroom observation amidst the new normal of education. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education*, 1(4), 281-296. <https://doi.org/10.35912/jshe.v1i4.721>

Caratiquit, S. D., & Pablo, L. M. (2021). Length of Service and Resistance to Change: Implications for RPMS Implementation Among MAPEH Teachers. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 30(4), 567-580.

Carter, R. S. & Nunan, D. (2001). *Teaching English to speakers of other language*. Cambridge: CUP. [https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=NHxOXpII6ssC&oi=fnd&pg=PR6&dq=Carter,+R.+S.+%26+Nunan,+D.+\(2001\).+Teaching+English+to+speakers+of+other+language.+Cambridge:+CUP.&ots=JOTMQn7Rqw&sig=RhkUzU9Wwzqqwi_HcEhjpDWFmUI&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=NHxOXpII6ssC&oi=fnd&pg=PR6&dq=Carter,+R.+S.+%26+Nunan,+D.+(2001).+Teaching+English+to+speakers+of+other+language.+Cambridge:+CUP.&ots=JOTMQn7Rqw&sig=RhkUzU9Wwzqqwi_HcEhjpDWFmUI&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false)

Castillo, E. (2021). Adjusting to the new normal education: Perceptions and experiences of fellow junior high school teachers on the conduct of classroom observation this COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR)*. ISSN: 2643-9670. Vol. 5 Issue 4, April - 2021, Pages: 41-44. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Eleanor-Castillo>

2/publication/350515482_Adjusting_to_the_New_Normal_Education_Perceptions_and_Experiences_of_Fellow_Junior_High_School_Teachers_on_the_Conduct_of_Class_Observation_this_COVID-19_Pandemic/links/608c014d299bf1ad8d6a892b/Adjusting-to-the-New-Normal-Education-Perceptions-and-Experiences-of-Fellow-Junior-High-School-Teachers-on-the-Conduct-of-Class-Observation-this-COVID-19-Pandemic.pdf

Co, A. G. E., Abella, C. R. G. & De Jesus, F. S. (2021). Teaching Outside Specialization from the Perspective of Science Teachers. *Open Access Library Journal*, 8, 1-13. doi: 10.4236/oalib.1107725.

Corcelles, R. D., Almonte, C. J., Valdehueza, R. R., Pagalan, R. T. & Maloloy-on, M. C. (2020). The Impact of Classroom Management Approaches of Secondary Teachers. *SMCC Higher Education Research Journal (Teacher Education Journal)*, 2(1). https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Melisa-Maloloy-On/publication/345028681_The_Impact_of_Classroom_Management_Approaches_of_Secondary_Teachers/links/63edc52951d7af05402b747a/The-Impact-of-Classroom-Management-Approaches-of-Secondary-Teachers.pdf

Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective Teacher Professional Development*. Palo Alto, CA: Learning Policy Institute. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED606743>

De la Cruz, D. (2019). Effectiveness of class observation to the performance of teachers in public elementary school in the division of Antipolo. *Volume 9, Issue No.3*. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=De+la+Cruz%2C+D.+%282019%29.+Effectiveness+of+class+observation+to+the+performance+of+teachers+in+public+elementary+school+in+the+division+of+Antipolo.+Volume+9%2C+Issue+No.3.&btnG=

Department of Education (2017). National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2017/08/11/do-42-s-2017-national-adoption-and-implementation-of-the-philippine-professional-standards-for-teachers/>

Department of Education - Bureau of Human Resource and Organizational Development (2018). *The Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) Manual for Teachers and School Heads*. http://depedcapiz.ph/downloads/RPMS_Manual.pdf

Department of Education (2023). *Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System – Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST)* (DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DM_s2023_008.pdf

Driessen, E. P., Knight, J. K., Smith, M. K., & Ballen, C. J. (2020). Demystifying the Meaning of Active Learning in Postsecondary Biology Education. *CBE Life Sci. Educ.* 19 (4), ar52. doi:10.1187/cbe.20-04-0068

Englatierra-Bilog, R. & Manoos, L. (2023). Preparedness of Public Elementary School Teachers in Performing Their Teaching Tasks Before, During, and after Classroom Observation in Lopez East District, Division of Quezon. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 11(3), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191253>

Fayo, C. L. & Hilario, C. R. (2023). Effectiveness of Classroom Observation on Teachers' Performance. *Industry and Academic Research Review*, 4 (1), 472-478. <https://www.neliti.com/publications/583613/effectiveness-of-classroom-observation-on-teachers-performance>

Garcia, R., Narca, J., Narca, J., Mariano, L., & Fronda, J. (2020). Analysis of senior high school -accountancy, business and management strand teachers performance. *International Journal of Research -Granthaalayah*, 8(1), 131-137. <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v8.i1.2020.260>

Ghavifekr, S., Husain, H., Rsdan, N. A., & Hamat, Z. W. (2019). Clinical supervision: towards effective classroom teaching, *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 7 (4), 30-42. <https://borneojournal.um.edu.my/index.php/MOJES/article/view/20059>

Hall, G., & Hord, S. (2015). *Implementing change: Patterns, principles, and potholes* (2010). *Reference and Research Book News*, 25(4). https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Hall%2C+G.%2C+%26+Hord%2C+S.+%282015%29.+Implementing+change%3A+Patterns%2C+principles%2C+and+potholes+%282010%29.+Reference+and+Research+Book+News%2C+25%284%29.&btnG=

Lopez, M. C. A. (2016). Classroom supervisory practices and their relationship to teacher effectiveness as perceived by secondary teachers. *SMCC Higher Education Research Journal*, 2, 119-131. <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=9773>

Mamaug, R. (2022). Results-Based Performance Management System: Its Implementation Challenges in San Antonio Elementary School. *International Journal of Arts, Sciences and Education*, 3(1), 1–10. <https://www.mail.ijase.org/index.php/ijase/article/view/90>

Manito, A. (2021). Characterizing Proficient Teachers as Teacher-Leaders in a Public Secondary School of Leyte Division. <https://www.scienceopen.com/hosted-document?doi=10.14293/S2199-1006.1.SOR-.PPPQKT.v1>

McCombes, S. (2023). Descriptive Research | Definition, Types, Methods & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>

Melati (2019). The role of the principal of Madrasa as a supervisor in developing teacher professional competence in Mts. Al Muslim in Proceeding of International Conference on Islamic Educational Management, 246-253. <https://conference.uinsu.ac.id/index.php/iciem/>

Notre Dame of Dadiangas University (2022). Competence of NDDU-IBED MAPEH Teachers. General Santos, Philippines. <https://www.nddu.edu.ph/research/competence-of-nddu-ibed-mapeh-teachers/>

Raza, M., Waheed, S. A., Gilani, N. (2023). Digital Citizenship for Cyber Smart Students: A Framework for Schools in Pakistan. Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS), 43(1),1-8. <http://pjss.bzu.edu.pk/index.php/pjss/article/view/1183>

Republic Act No. 10533. Official Gazette. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republicact-no-10533/>

Riego de Dios, E. E. (2020). Emotional intelligence and work values of selected instructors from a teacher education institution. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research, 4 (5), 92-97. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3614929>

Samonte, K. & Guzman, P. (2019). ICT Competencies among Public Secondary School MAPEH Teachers: An Assessment. JPAIR Institutional Research. <https://doi.org/10.7719/irj.v12i1.743>

Sebastian, M. F. (2020). Using songs as springboard to teaching poetry and narratives towards improved comprehension. Int J Acad App Res. 4:72- 78. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3639718

Smith, J. (2020). The Role of Classroom Observation in Evaluating Teacher Performance. Journal of Education Evaluation. 15 (2) 123-136.

Suparto (2020). Improving the learning quality of Math teachers through the academic supervision with technique of class observation. International Research Based Educational Journal, 2 (1), 21-24. <https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/documents/detail/2379734>

Tawalbeh, T. I. (2020). Instructors' perceptions of EFL supervisors' classroom observation practices at university level. International Journal of Education and Practice, 8 (1), 45-56. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.61.2020.81.45.56>

Thomas, L. (2020). Stratified sampling, definition, guide and examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/stratified-sampling/#:~:text=What%20is%20stratified%20sampling%3F,using%20another%20probability%20sampling%20method>

Wairimu, M. J., (2016). Teachers' perception on classroom observation and checking of pupils' exercise books by head teachers on performance of duty in primary schools in Nakuru North District, Kenya. Journal of Education & Social Policy, 3 (3), 80-87. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Wairimu%2C+M.+J.%2C+%282016%29.+Teachers%E2%80%99+perception+on+classroom+observation+and+checking+of+pupils%E2%80%99+exercise+books+by+head+teachers+on+performance+of+duty+in+primary+schools+in+Nakuru+North+District%2C+Kenya.+Journal+of+Education+%26+Social+Policy%2C+3+%283%29%2C+80-87.+&btnG=

Zaman, S., Waheed, S. A., & Gilani, N. (2022). An Assessment of the Usefulness of Online Performance Evaluation Reports (PERs) in Comparison to Manual Reports in Schools. Pakistan Journal of Educational Research, 5(4), 321-333. <https://pjer.org/index.php/pjer/article/view/713>

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